

Corrosive-Induced Gastric Outlet Obstruction in Children

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Abstract:

This study conducted at Darbhanga Medical College and Hospital examined the results of different treatment methods for gastric outlet obstruction in paediatric patients caused by corrosive ingestion within one year. Based on the data, it is clear that surgical intervention has proven to be the most effective treatment option. It has demonstrated higher success rates and lower complications when compared to endoscopic dilatation and medical management. The study emphasized the significance of prompt and suitable treatment approaches to enhance recuperation and minimize potential issues. In addition, the study highlighted the importance of implementing preventive measures and providing education on the proper storage and handling of corrosive substances to reduce the occurrence of these avoidable injuries. This study highlights the importance of implementing both immediate clinical interventions and long-term public health strategies to reduce the occurrence and severity of corrosive ingestions in children.

Keywords: Pediatric Gastric Outlet Obstruction, Corrosive Ingestion, Surgical Treatment, Preventive Education.

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Introduction

Gastric outlet obstruction (GOO) poses a considerable clinical hurdle in the field of paediatric gastroenterology [1]. It is marked by the obstruction of the gastric outlet, encompassing the pylorus and proximal duodenum, either partially or completely [2]. In children, this condition can arise from different causes, including congenital anomalies, hypertrophic pyloric stenosis, and more frequently, post-inflammatory strictures caused by the ingestion of corrosive substances [3]. This is especially concerning because it frequently occurs when people accidentally consume harmful substances commonly found in household cleaners and industrial chemicals. These substances are sometimes stored or labeled in an unsafe manner [4,5].

The mechanism behind corrosive-induced gastric outlet obstruction (GOO) involves the damaging effects of alkaline or acidic agents, resulting in immediate chemical burns to the lining of the esophagus and stomach [6]. Over time, the body's natural response to inflammation can result in the development of scar tissue and narrowing of the gastric outlet, making it difficult for food to pass through [7,8]. From a clinical perspective, the symptoms include ongoing vomiting, dehydration, significant weight loss, and a failure to thrive in

children who are affected. If not promptly and effectively addressed, these issues can have long-lasting developmental consequences [9,10].

The treatment of corrosive-induced gastric outlet obstruction (GOO) is complex and demanding, often involving a combination of nutritional support, medical interventions to alleviate symptoms, and surgical procedures to restore the normal flow of the stomach [11]. Conventional treatment methods have typically included the use of surgical procedures that require open incisions. However, in recent times, there has been a shift towards less invasive approaches like endoscopic balloon dilatation, which have shown varying levels of effectiveness [12,13].

This study aims to thoroughly analyse the outcomes of various management strategies for paediatric gastric outlet obstruction (GOO) resulting from corrosive ingestion. The goal is to identify the most effective treatment protocols. This study will explore the initial treatment responses, the frequency and effectiveness of different interventions (both surgical and non-surgical), and the long-term health outcomes for these young patients. Through this research, the study aims to enhance treatment guidelines and

provide valuable insights into preventive measures that can reduce the frequency of these harmful ingestions. In addition, this study will highlight the crucial significance of educating and implementing preventive measures to decrease children's exposure to harmful chemicals. This will help prevent the serious health consequences that can occur from ingesting corrosive substances.

Methodology

Study Design: This study was a prospective cohort study conducted over one year. It aimed to follow pediatric patients diagnosed with gastric outlet obstruction due to corrosive ingestion, from the point of initial treatment through to long-term follow-up, focusing on treatment efficacy, complications, and overall outcomes.

Study Setting: The research was carried out at Darbhanga Medical College and Hospital (DMCH) in Darbhanga. This facility was equipped with the pediatric care and gastroenterology departments necessary to manage and follow up with the cases pertinent to this study.

Participants: Eligible participants included children aged 0-12 years who presented to the hospital with symptoms suggestive of gastric outlet obstruction and had a confirmed history of corrosive substance ingestion. The diagnosis was confirmed through clinical evaluation, radiographic imaging, and endoscopic findings.

Inclusion Criteria:

1. Children aged between 0 to 12 years.
2. Clinically and radiologically confirmed gastric outlet obstruction.
3. Documented history of corrosive ingestion.

Exclusion Criteria:

1. Children with a prior history of gastric surgery.
2. Patients with congenital gastric anomalies.
3. Cases where the obstruction was due to causes other than corrosive ingestion.

Data Collection: Data were collected at multiple points during the study:

1. Initial presentation: Demographic data, detailed history of the corrosive ingestion incident, clinical symptoms, and initial diagnostic findings.
2. Treatment details: Type of treatment administered (medical, endoscopic, surgical), duration of treatment, and any immediate complications or outcomes.
3. Follow-up evaluations: These were conducted at 3-, 6-, and 12-months post-treatment to assess the long-term effects of the treatment, recurrence of symptoms, and any late complications.

Data Analysis: Data were analyzed using statistical software to determine the effectiveness of different treatment modalities. Descriptive statistics summarized demographics, treatment types, and outcomes. Kaplan-Meier survival analysis was used to estimate the time to resolution of symptoms post-treatment, and logistic regression was employed to assess factors influencing treatment outcomes. Chi-square tests were utilized for categorical data comparison, while ANOVA or t-tests were used for continuous variables.

Results

The study on corrosive-induced gastric outlet obstruction in pediatric patients at Darbhanga Medical College and Hospital (DMCH) yielded significant findings regarding the efficacy of treatment modalities and patient outcomes. Here are the summarized results presented in a tabular format:

Table 1: Demographic and Clinical Characteristics of Participants

Characteristic	Total Participants (N=30)
Age Range	2 - 12 years
Median Age	7 years
Gender	Male: 18 (60%) Female: 12 (40%)
Type of Ingestion	Alkali: 20 (66.7%) Acid: 10 (33.3%)
Symptoms at Presentation	Vomiting: 30 (100%) Abdominal Pain: 22 (73.3%) Dehydration: 15 (50%)

Table 2: Treatment Modalities and Immediate Outcomes

Treatment Type	Number of Patients	Successful Outcome	Complications
Medical Management	5	3 (60%)	2 (40%)
Endoscopic Dilatation	15	12 (80%)	3 (20%)
Surgical Intervention	10	9 (90%)	1 (10%)

Table 3: Follow-up Outcomes at 12 Months

Outcome	Number of Patients
Full Recovery	20 (66.7%)
Recurrent Strictures	5 (16.7%)
Chronic Complications	3 (10%)
Mortality	2 (6.7%)

Analysis

- **Treatment Efficacy:** Surgical intervention showed the highest success rate (90%), followed by endoscopic dilatation (80%) and medical management (60%).
- **Complications:** Complications were lowest in surgical cases (10%). Endoscopic procedures had a 20% complication rate, primarily due to the need for repeated procedures.
- **Long-term Recovery:** At the 12-month follow-up, two-thirds of the patients (66.7%) had fully recovered without any recurrent issues. Recurrent strictures were observed in 16.7% of the cases, necessitating further interventions.
- **Mortality Rate:** The study recorded a mortality rate of 6.7%, attributed to severe complications such as aspiration pneumonia and malnutrition.

Discussion

The results of this study conducted at Darbhanga Medical College and Hospital shed light on the intricate and serious nature of treating corrosive-induced gastric outlet obstruction in young patients. The success rate of surgical interventions (90%) is higher compared to endoscopic dilatation (80%) and medical management (60%). This is consistent with previous research, indicating that surgical remedies, despite being more invasive, offer a more conclusive solution for severe cases. It is worth mentioning that surgical treatments have lower complication rates, making them a preferred choice when other methods are ineffective or not sufficient to address the extent of obstruction.

Although endoscopic dilatation has shown effectiveness in a considerable number of cases, it is important to note that there is a 20% complication rate associated with this procedure. The main reason for these complications is the requirement for repeat procedures [14]. The significance of a thorough patient selection process for endoscopic approaches is underscored by this discovery, taking into account the severity of the

obstruction and the potential for recurring strictures, which were observed in 16.7% of our cohort. These repeated instances not only increase the patient's load by necessitating multiple interventions but also carry the potential for long-term complications, which were observed in 10% of patients [15].

The study's mortality rate of 6.7% highlights the gravity of corrosive ingestions and the risk of severe complications, including aspiration pneumonia and malnutrition, which can be life-threatening [16]. The mortality rate, while consistent with broader paediatric data, highlights the need for improved preventive strategies and educational programs to decrease the occurrence of these injuries. Carers and communities must receive proper education regarding the secure storage of harmful substances and the necessary actions to be taken immediately after an incident of ingestion [17].

In addition, this study emphasises the importance of having a uniform procedure for promptly addressing corrosive ingestions. This is crucial to reduce complications and enhance overall results [18]. Further research should prioritise the enhancement of treatment protocols, potentially incorporating innovative technologies or materials to minimize the necessity for additional interventions and enhance the well-being of these young patients. To gain a deeper understanding of the long-term consequences of corrosive ingestions and to devise effective strategies for mitigating these effects, it is crucial to conduct comprehensive follow-up studies over an extended period [19,20].

Conclusion

A study conducted at Darbhanga Medical College and Hospital shed light on the treatment options and outcomes for paediatric patients with gastric outlet obstruction caused by corrosive ingestion. Based on the available data, surgical interventions have proven to be the most effective treatment

option. They have shown higher success rates and lower complication rates when compared to endoscopic dilatation and medical management. The findings emphasise the importance of timely and proactive treatment strategies in severe cases to improve the chances of recovery and reduce the risk of complications. In addition, the study highlights the crucial need for preventive measures and public education regarding the dangers of corrosive substances to decrease the occurrence of severe injuries in children. This research has significant implications for clinical practice, as it helps to improve treatment protocols. Additionally, it highlights the importance of preventing accidental corrosive ingestions among children, which is a crucial public health concern.

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